

Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction on the Relationship between Leadership Styles and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour in Nigerian Health Sector: Conceptual Model

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Abstract

Scholarly knowledge of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) has developed significantly in both the private and public sectors. Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) has attracted the attention of many academicians and practitioners due to its proven significance towards organizational effectiveness. Despite the importance of OCB, there is still lack of studies on how organization can encourage their employees to exhibit such behaviour. Therefore, this paper aims to address the gap with Job Satisfaction, Servant leadership Transactional and Transformational leadership style which has been considered as a very important factor effecting employee's behaviour and attitudes in an organization. Specifically, this paper aims to determine the mediating role of Job Satisfaction among public health employees. Moreover it will identify which facets of leadership style and Job Satisfaction (JS) that are the most important drivers of organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) and a quantitative research method be used for data collection. This research will help organizational managers and government bodies to understand the factors affecting OCB and a leadership style with Job Satisfaction among public health employees and thus enhance their OCB and as well performance.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Leadership style, Organizational Citizenship Behaviour, Public Health Employees

INTRODUCTION

The field of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour OCB has become an interesting social behaviour field of research and having the attention of many researchers. Many studies have revealed that OCB contributes in many ways to an organization, such as increasing productivity, increasing organizations effectiveness and competency, fulfilling its purposes and objectives and increasing the moral of employees (Demired 2018). The OCB is not aim to fulfil employee's personal needs and benefits but to improve organizational engagement, and OCB is important for both the organization and individual because it improve overall institutional performance by maintaining reciprocal relations among managers and employees attached to different sections, improve unity and cohesion of the institution and minimize the need of scare resource allocation. (Mehdizadeh, 2018). OCB Literature has indicated that a good number of antecedents have been found to influence OCB. However, a few studies Ehrhart, (2004); Vondey, (2010); Walumbwa, Hartnell & Oke, (2010) have related servant leadership as one among the antecedent to OCB, and have found positive relationship. According to a study carried out by Vondey (2010) Bambale, Faridahwati Mohd, Chandrakantan (2015) revealed that servant leadership significantly but partially correlates with OCB, thus suggesting more studies.

Moreover, Transactional and Transformational leadership style also are among the significant factors found to influence employee OCB.(Ojokuku, 2012). The main leadership styles that have received empirical attention in relation to OCB over the years include transformational leadership (Asgari , 2008; Bettencourt, 2004; Schlechter & Engelbrecht, 2006; Vigoda-Gadot, 2007), transactional leadership (Bettencourt, 2004; Vigoda-Gadot, 2007) and charismatic leadership (Babcock-Roberson & Strickland, 2010). However the major concern proposed for this study is the Transformational and Transactional leadership style. And in contrast with some of the previous literature on the

relationship between Job Satisfaction JS and OCB suffers from inconsistent findings. While some studies support the positive relationship between JS and OCB others have concluded that there is no relationship between these variables. Ngadiman and Ratmawati (2013) found that JS as a whole has no significant relationship with OCB; however promotion and enabling work environment partially influence OCB. Many studies from various sectors and employment supported the significant relationship between JS and OCB (Ibrahim and Aslinda, 2013; Unal, 2013; Mehboob, 2012; Mohammad, 2011; Foote and Tang, 2008). Ibrahim, (2013) suggested that employees with high satisfaction were likely to portray positive behaviours such as OCB as an expression of “payback” by way of being thankful to the organization. In addition to that, JS and OCB have been empirically found to promote the efficient and effective functioning of organizations (Organ, 1988; Podsakoff, 1997).

Perhaps, if employees are being treated with supportive Human Resource Management (HRM) practices, they show a propensity to exhibit higher levels of OCB (Narang & Singh, 2012; Sivapragasam & Raya, 2018). This implies that human input in terms of work by well-motivated and productive human beings will yield the required result. Concepts that have been found to have positive impact on employees wellbeing and employee performance of some organizations, which could also apply to health organizations, include Transactional and Transformational leadership style and Job satisfaction (Chang Chiang and Van Dyne and Pierce 2014). Impact, studies revealed that, the health sector is one of the most important in supporting the livelihood and overall development of many organizations. (Bades, & Moringa, 2015). Health care is labour-intensive, making human resources one of the most important inputs in health care delivery (WHO 2013a:3). During African Conference on the MDGs, it was stated that insufficient health personnel, in terms of numbers and level of performance, is one major constraint in achieving the millennium development goals (MDGs) Some of the actions proposed to rectify this situation include improving the motivation, behaviour, retention, productivity and performance of health workers (High-level forum, 2014:7; Stilwell, 2011). However, health institution in Africa including Nigeria faces problems and challenges. The fact that the problems and challenges were largely caused by employee attitudes such as leadership ineffectiveness and low employee morale, suggests that a more ethical leadership behaviour and style could help in turning around the ailing Nigerian health organizations.

Statement of Research Problem

Having been introduced to the background and practical issues related to this study, thus in line with the entire observed literature gap, suggesting the need for more studies, there is no open deliberation among researchers on the mediating effect of Job satisfaction JS on the relationship between leadership style and OCB. However, few studies have investigated the relationships between servant leadership, transactional and transformational leadership style and OCB generally (Ehrhart, 2004; Walumbwa et al, 2010; Hu and Liden, 2011; Güçel and Begeç, 2012; Hunter, 2013, Bambale et al 2015). However, except Bambale et al. (2015) Walumbwa et al. (2010) all the previous studies were concentrated in the Asia and Europe. Hence, none of the previous studies has focused on the employees of health organizations.

Yet, there remains unclear understanding as to how the human resource management, the most crucial fillers of employee directing and supervising system in an organization, could contribute to the employee OCB in relation to in consistent finding on the relationship among the construct especially in the Nigerian health organizations. Studies revealed that Nigeria health system faces difficult challenges such as shortage of health workers, increased caseloads for health workers due to migration of skilled health personnel, lack of adequate working facilities, good welfare, helping behaviour, and motivation that affect both the general population and health personnel (Dielem, Coung, Anh, and Martineau, 2013:1). Thus, a prerequisite for a well-functioning health system is well-motivated staffs that carry out their work according to standards set by the organisation and even go beyond, i.e. OCB. (Dielem, 2013; Awases, Gbary, Nyoni, and Chatora, 2014:53-57).

This paper is motivated and justified by two strong reasons (i.e. primary and secondary): (1) primarily, literature reveals no prior study on the mediating role of job satisfaction JS on the relationship between leadership style and OCB, suggesting the existence of theoretical gap in the literature, (2) At a secondary level, this study is justified because of the presence of inefficiency and ineffectiveness of the Nigerian health organizations, especially public health institutions.

Hypotheses Development

Meanwhile, in order to address the above contradiction thus, this paper develops the following hypotheses to examine the relationship between the mediating role of Job Satisfaction, leadership style and OCB among employees of some health institutions in Bauchi state.

H1: There is a significant relationship between Servant leadership and OCB

H2: There is a significant relationship between Transactional leadership styles and OCB

H3: There is a significant relationship between Transformational leadership styles and OCB

H4: There is a significant relationship between Servant leadership and JS

H5: There is a significant relationship between Transactional Leadership styles and JS

H6: There is a significant relationship between Transformational leadership styles and JS

H7: There is a significant relationship between Job satisfaction and OCB

H8: Job satisfaction mediate the relationship between Servant leadership and OCB

H9: Job satisfaction mediate the relationship between Transactional leadership styles and OCB

H10: Job satisfaction mediate the relationship between Transformational leadership styles and OCB

Perhaps, this paper is an attempt to propose a replicated model to clarify the actual relationship between the construct and OCB in a new environment and context. Precisely, the study proposes to test the relationship between the mediating role of job satisfaction, servant leadership, Transformational leadership, Transactional leadership style and OCB which still remain inconclusive, in Nigeria's health sector.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

Servant leadership, Transactional, Transformational and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB)

A large number of studies on servant leadership behaviour were undertaken to explain the principles and performance of servant leadership (Dennis & Bocarnea, 2005; Geller, 2009; Han, Kakabadse & Kakabadse, 2010; Irving & McIntosh, 2009; Sendjaya, Sarros & Santora, 2008). However, a few studies (Ehrhart, 2004; Vondey, 2010; Walumbwa, Hartnell & Oke, 2010) have related servant leadership to OCB, and have found positive relationship. One of the prominent early studies that attempted to investigate the effect of servant leadership on OCB is Ehrhart (2004). Results of the study demonstrated that servant leadership indirectly influences helping behaviour and conscientiousness. Again, a study carried out by Vondey (2010) revealed that servant leadership significantly but partially correlates with OCB, thus suggesting more studies.

Additionally, Bambale et.al, (2015) have empirically found a positive relationship between the servant leadership behaviour and OCB revealed that four servant leader behaviours including emotional healing, creating value for the community, conceptual skills and putting subordinates first have significant relationships with the overall OCB-I. Only one servant leader behaviour, namely, helping subordinates grow and succeed did not significantly relate to the overall performance of employee OCB-I and recommend further research to consider mediating the construct with job satisfaction.. According to Greenleaf, (1977) as cited by Bambale, Faridahwati, Chandrakantan (2012) Research establishes that servant leadership may be more conducive to organizational citizenship behaviours due to its focus on follower development, community building, authentic leadership, since Servant leadership is a leadership style where leaders place the needs of their subordinates before their own needs and centre their efforts on helping subordinates grow to reach their maximum potential and achieve optimal organizational and career success. Looking at the results of the previous studies which suggest inconclusiveness, and considering that servant leadership and OCB study is still new, there is need for more research.

Transactional and Transformational Leadership style have empirically found a significance relationship and are the significant factors found to influence employee OCB. (Ojokuku, 2012 Bass 2015). The main leadership styles that have received empirical attention in relation to OCB over the years include transformational leadership (Asgari,2008; Bettencourt, 2004; Schlechter & Engelbrecht, 2006; Vigoda-Gadot, 2007), transactional leadership (Bettencourt, 2004; Vigoda-Gadot, 2007) and charismatic leadership (Babcock-Roberson & Strickland, 2010). Bass (1985) identified two dimensions of transactional leadership consisting of management by exception and contingent reward that found to have significance relationship to employee OCB.

Bass (1985) equally, identified three main behaviours of effective transactional leaders as: (1) recognizing what followers want from the work organization; (2) trying to see that employees get what they want from their work organization if their performance warrants (i.e., exchange rewards and promises); and (3) trying to be responsive to followers' immediate self-interests if could be met by getting the work done. It could, therefore, be understood how a favourable cost-benefit analysis is important to a transactional leader. After the initial exploratory factor analysis, Bass (1985) identified a four factor structure consisting of charisma, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individual consideration. At a later period, Bass (2000) identified four critical transformational leadership dimensions including, individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation and idealized influence that relate to an employee OCB. Moreover, Bass (1985) transformational leaders are regarded as charismatic leaders who offer a vision and a mission to employees. Such leaders will try to instil pride and gain respect and trust from employees so that the organization can achieve the required outcomes and thus, leads to OCB.

Servant leadership, Transactional, Transformational and Job Satisfaction (JS)

Only a few studies considered the effect of servant leadership behaviour and job satisfaction on OCB despite the importance of servant leadership and the job satisfaction in our contemporary public and private organizations (Albart, 2015; Organ, 2016). Servant leadership is a leadership style that places the followers' interests over and above the leader's own interest (Joseph & Winston, 2005). According to Odunlade (2012) Job defined as a regular activity performed in exchange for payment, especially as one's trade, occupation, or profession is referred to as job. It may also be assumed to be a position in which one is employed. Job satisfaction is also the reflection of a good compensation program. The happier people are within their job, the more satisfied they are said to be. According to Berry (1997) as cited in Odunlade (2012), job satisfaction is defined as an individual's reaction to the job experience. There are various components that are considered by Berry to be vital to job satisfaction and they include the following: pay, promotion, benefits, supervisor, co-workers, work conditions, communication, safety, productivity, and the work itself. He said that these variables are important because all of them influence the way a person feels about his job, though each of these figures into an individual's job satisfaction differently. Previous studies found that good leadership leads to employee satisfaction, thereby to treat work and activities as important thus encourage them to perform with high obligation and uprightness (Hakim, 2014).

Transformational and Transactional Leadership styles are factors that have been regarded as primary for organizational success and have found to relate with an employee job satisfaction (Spector, 1997; Schnake, 1995; Henne and Locke, 1985, Bass, 1985). Empirical research has focused on four major categories of antecedents: individual (or employee) characteristics, task characteristics, organizational characteristics, and leadership behaviours, which concentrated primarily on employee attitudes, dispositions, and leader supportiveness. (Bateman & Organ, 1983; Organ, 1988; Smith, 1983). The relevance of transformational and Transactional leadership to employees' job satisfaction is not restricted to a particular organizational setting. Prior studies have consistently found that transformational and transactional behaviours occur and enhance followers' job satisfaction in various organizational settings, including educational, industrial, military, health and volunteer settings (Braun S, Peus C, Weisweiler S, Frey D 2013 and Rowold J, Rohmann, 2009). For instance, (Yang F-H, Wu M, Chang C-C, Chien Y, 2011) found that followers' positive perceptions of transformational behaviours by leaders (or supervisors) lead to stronger identification with the organization, increased internalization of organizational goals, and improved job satisfaction.

The transformational leadership is important for individuals employee who work in rapidly changing environments with divers set of personalities, it strengthen their organizational commitment and job satisfaction (Griffith, 2004). Indeed, transformational leadership too is important to any organization that experiences environmental changes, including public sector organizations, which are commonly perceived as undergoing minimal organizational change. In a similar vein, a study by Wright and Pandey (2011) suggests that transformational leadership behaviours are not limited by procedural constraints and rules in organizations with hierarchical authority structures. Such organizations can opt to change leadership styles even if their hierarchical decision-making structures may constrain transformational leadership behaviours to transactional leadership behaviour.

In a particular vain, scholars have acknowledged the importance of transformational and transactional leadership in enhancing the job satisfaction with divergent views of staff in healthcare industries (Nielsen, Yarker, Randall, Munir, 2009 and Luo, Fang, Fang, 2015). Mostly employees in the healthcare sector often work in high pressure environments. Supervisors' transformational behaviours can establish a sense of self-control and competence among employees and thereby enhance job satisfaction (Nielsen K, et al.). According to Andrews and Dziegielewski (2015) explain that nursing staff generally prefer supervisors with transformational behaviours that address employees' individual needs than transactional. Thus, transformational leadership can reduce nursing staff turnover owing to low job satisfaction. This reasoning leads to the need for more research.

Job satisfaction and OCB

Previous literature on the relationship between JS and OCB suffers from inconsistent findings. While some studies support the positive relationship between JS and OCB others have concluded that there is no relationship between these variables. Researchers studied the relationship between JS with OCB for two main reasons. First, the norm of reciprocity (Schnake et al., 1995) which occurs when the organization gave the support and the good response to its employees; in return the employee will not hesitate and compelled to give a positive response to the organization. This also consistent with Boulanger (2013) study where he posited that the ranges employees consider in the norm of reciprocity are greatly in the variable of job context and social exchange relationship among co-workers and leaders. Boulanger (2013) also posited that the difficulty of task perhaps will encourage and predicted OCB among employee. The second reason is psychological. When employees are satisfied and receive a positive response from their work, they simply show the pro-social behaviour (Unal, 2013).

In contrast with some of the previous research on JS and OCB, Chen, (1998) failed to find a significant relationship between these two variables, and set a single-item scale to measure overall JS and adapted three dimensions of the OCB scale (altruism, conscientiousness and sportsmanship) to create an overall OCB score. Driscoll and Randall (1999) did not find any relationship between intrinsic JS and OCB at individual and organizational level. Although many studies have measured how people are satisfied with their job in several organizations but it has a significant difference across cultures (Unal, 2013; Robbins, 2013; Kumari and Rachna, 2011). Global study of JS levels of workers in 23 countries indicates employees in Western cultures have higher level of JS compare to those in the Eastern cultures (Robbins, 2013). These findings raise the question of whether there are other variables that comprise employee morale (e.g., trust, more specific forms of satisfaction, etc.) whose effects may also be important to examine. In addition to that, since JS and OCB have been empirically found to promote the efficient and effective functioning of organizations (Organ, 1988; Podsakoff, 1997) continuous study on this aspect is still needed.

The Conceptual Model

Employee OCB can be as a result of satisfaction with organizational leadership style and experienced in the course of normal day-to-day relationships with the leader. This study is indeed going to be concerned with investigating the mediating role of job satisfaction on the relationship between leadership style on the employee OCB. The variables of this study are as follows: the independent variables leadership styles are Servant leadership behaviour, Transactional and Transformational, the dependent variable is organizational citizenship behaviours (OCB), and the Mediator Variable is Employee satisfaction. The model is as follows:

Conceptual Framework

The model is as follows:

Source: The Researcher (2023)

Figure 1 Model of the relationship between Leadership style, job satisfaction and employee organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB).

Moreover, it has been suggested that, the leadership style and job satisfaction predicts employee OCB (Ehrhart, 2004 and organ, 2018). The theoretical framework for this argument is that leaders who serve their followers would produce followers who serve others. Thus, a leader is a role model for followers, and employee OCB is influenced by models (Smith, Organ & Near, 1983). People learn from observing others and modelling what they see, as in if employees experience and observe a leader serving others, followers themselves will in turn serve others. This service could entail helping co-workers, promoting the organization to outsiders, and encouraging others to express their ideas and opinions, thus performing organizational citizenship behaviour (OCBs).

Organizational Citizenship Behaviour Dimensions

OCB construct has been conceptualized in several ways (e.g., Bateman & Organ, 1983; Organ, 1988; Smith, 1983; Van Dyne, Graham & Dienesch, 1994; Williams & Anderson, 1991), thus indicating the lack of consensus in its dimensions (Khalid, 2005; Podsakoff 2000). However, one of the popular OCB construct (Podsakoff et al., 2000) has been considered for this study. Seven common dimensions had been created based on examination of the literature by

Podsakoff (2000). These dimensions are helping behaviour, sportsmanship, organizational loyalty, organizational compliance, individual initiative, civic virtue and self-development. But there are some conceptual overlaps between concepts such as altruism and courtesy of Organ's OCB.(2008).

Servant Leadership Dimensions

In attempts to define the servant leadership construct, different numbers of inconsistent set of dimensions have been used by different authors (Barbuto & Wheeler, 2006; Page & Wong, 2000; Spears & Lawrence, 2002). Specifically, Vondey (2010) reported that 16 models of servant leadership have been found in the literature. Commonly used, Liden (2008) seven dimensions are operationalized below: The seven dimensions

- a. Behaving ethically: b. Helping subordinates grow and succeed: c. Empowering: d. Putting subordinates first:
- e. Conceptual skill: f. Creating value for the community: g. Emotional healing:

Transactional and Transformational Leadership Style Dimensions

Bass (1985) identified two dimensions of transactional leadership consisting of management by exception and contingent reward. Contingent reward involves rewarding the subordinates only when assignments are carried out as "transacted". Management by exception is concerned with the leader's proactive intervention when it is clear that unforeseen problem could potentially hamper the subordinate's performance.

At a later period, Bass (2000) identified four critical transformational leadership dimensions including, individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation and idealized influence.

Dimensions of job satisfaction

Vroom (1962) classified job satisfaction into 7 dimensions, namely; organizational, promotion, job content, superior, reward, working environment and working partners. After piloting, twelve items were used to assess four of these job satisfaction dimensions (working partners, reward, and welfare, superior and job recognition). Items were removed from the leadership behaviour and job satisfaction domains after the pre-test in order for the tools to be relevant to the context and setting. Smith et al. (1969) indicated that there are five facets that are typically used in measuring JS including pay, promotions, relationship with co-workers, supervision or relationship with supervisor, and the work itself. Oshagbemi and Hickson (2003) indicated that pay affect the overall level of JS. Employees want their pay to be fair and adequate in order to meet their needs (Henne and Locke, 1985).

Theoretical Frame Work

The theoretical background for the study is going to be drive from the social exchange theory SET (Blau, 1964). In a related study A J Bambale et al 2015, Alfes, Shantz, Truss, & Soane (2013) adopted Social Exchange Theory as the theoretical framework in evaluating the link with servant leadership behaviour, human resource management (HRM) practice and OCB. Social Exchange Theory (SET) is constructed on the principle of reciprocity and felt obligation, signifying that while employees have fair treatment from a specific source, in return they are expected to respond with positive attitudes and behaviours toward that specific party (Harris, Lavelle, & McMahan, 2018; Lavelle, Rupp, & Brockner, 2007; Rupp, Shao, Jones, & Liao, 2014). As per the social exchange view, HRM practices be able to deliver an encouraging indication to the employees regarding managements' concern for their welfare and wants to establish long-term relationship with them (Gould-Williams, 2016). Therefore, in return, employees are expected to exhibit positive attitudes and behaviours (Kim & Ko, 2014) Therefore, to examine the employee behavioural intention in the organizational setting SET is deemed to be the most appropriate theory (Kehoe & Wright,2013; Ko & Hur, 2014; Whitener, 2001).

The fundamental basis of social exchange theory is that relationships providing more benefits than costs will yield enduring mutual trust and attraction (Blau, 1964). These social transactions encompass both material benefits (i.e. salaries, bonuses, and allowances) and thus job satisfaction. (i.e. status, loyalty and approval; Yukl, 1994). Central to both social exchange theory and the norm of reciprocity is the concept of unspecified obligations. Unspecified obligations denote human behaviour that when one individual party does a favour to another, there exists an expectation of some future return from the other individual party. These obligations maybe enacted in the form of citizenship behaviours and over time, a pattern of reciprocity evolves, resulting in perceived balance in the exchange relationship (Blau, 1964; Gouldner, 1960; Rousseau, 1989). Citizenship behaviours are more likely to be under an individual's control, and hence more likely to be a salient mode of reciprocation (Organ, 1990). Exchange relationships with the organization and with one's immediate supervisor are of great significance to subordinate employees (Jawahar & Carr, 2007).

Based on the previously mentioned theorem of unspecified obligations which is central to both the social exchange theory and the norm of reciprocity, employees' exchange relationship with the organization is influenced greatly by

unspecified obligations. Therefore, employee OCB can be as a result of satisfaction with some organizational practices and consequent experience of belonging for the organization by the employees. Therefore, this paper will investigate the relationship between mediating role of job satisfaction, leadership style and OCB.

Contextualizing the Study

Nigeria being the giant of African and it is a very crucial market to Africa's business and economic development (Abdul, Ahmed and Samrat 2014). However, Nigeria remains a corrupt nation and grossly underdeveloped even in terms of health care system delivery that is vital for human survival. (Adenuga, 2015). It is therefore, observed that Nigeria cannot develop with high level of corruption and inefficiency experienced in the countries health system. To develop the country, there is need to improve on the way to stop or minimize corruption and improve efficiency in the public health sector as well and to strengthen the private sector as it's an architect of any development (Akilu 2010; Wole-Rufa'i, 2016). The health sector is one of the most important in supporting the livelihood, good behaviour and development of Nigeria. (Bades, & Moringa, 2015). Health care is labour-intensive, making human resources one of the most important inputs in health care delivery (WHO 2003a:3). It is widely acknowledged that health workers are not producing the desired output of health interventions. Many have echoed this concern. There is a growing concern about the poor quality of health services rendered to the Nigerian population, even though the National Health Policy advocates for improved quality of services to be provided at health facilities in the country.

Also, there is a decline in the quality of health services available in the country, that most Nigerians prefer to be treated abroad, coupled with the long queues of clients and patients in most of our hospitals whether public or private. This assertion is supported by events that occurred in the recent past in our country Nigeria. On January, 2009, the ex-Governor of Yobe state, Alhaji Mamman Ali, died in the United States of America where he had gone to receive medical attention. Similarly, on February 21, 2009, when the Shehu of Borno, Alhaji Mustapha Umar El Kanemi, collapsed in his palace he was flown to a Cairo hospital in Egypt where he eventually died (Kolawole, 2009: 19). Perhaps, our late president, Umar Musa Yar'Adua was treated for acute pericarditis and chronic kidney problems, firstly in a German hospital and later on, in a Saudia Arabia hospital where he diet. Similarly, the current president of Nigeria Muhammadu Buhari was treated not long ago at the inception of his first tenure 2016 in UK. All these are sad commentaries on Nigeria's healthcare system. Moreover, the quality, efficiency and equity of services of health personnel are all dependent on the availability of skilled and competent health professionals when and where they are needed.

Against this background, this paper is concerned with making a meaningful contribution for the realization of the success of the present health sector performance from human resource organizational management perspective. This paper proposes a conceptual model comprising of three significant variables, namely servant leadership and leadership style as the independent variable while, job satisfaction as a mediating variable, and employee citizenship behaviour (OCB) as the dependent variable. Experiencing good leadership, job satisfaction for the organization among employees of this important organization is capable of positively affecting their morale, attitude and behaviour toward the organization. Specifically, the good feelings towards the organization can push them into activities that their formal jobs did not require them to perform (i.e., OCB). It has been well established in the literature that OCB influences effective functioning of organizations, and also leads to efficient allocation of resources (Organ, 1990). The proposed model which will empirically be tested using the employees of the health sector in Nigeria, which is aimed at providing viable strategy for solving the lingering problems of the Nigeria's health sector, and thus serve as a positive stimulus for improved performance of the sector.

This paper proposes a conceptual model comprising of five significant variables, namely servant leadership, transactional, transformational as the independent variables while, job satisfaction as a mediating variable, and employee citizenship behaviour (OCB) as the dependent variable. Experiencing good leadership, job satisfaction for the organization among employees of this important organization is capable of positively affecting their morale, attitude and behaviour toward the organization. Specifically, the good feelings towards the organization can push them into activities that their formal jobs did not require them to perform (i.e., OCB). It has been well established in the literature that OCB influences effective functioning of organizations, and also leads to efficient allocation of resources (Organ, 1990). The proposed model which will empirically be tested using the employees of the health sector in Nigeria, which is aimed at providing viable strategy for solving the lingering problems of the Nigeria's health sector, and thus serve as a positive stimulus for improved performance of the sector.

METHODOLOGY

Population and Sample of the study:

According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010) state that population of the study is the group of people, events or things of interest for which the researcher wants to make inferences based on the derived sample. This study will focus on the employees of Health institution in Nigeria. North-east has been selected for this study because it has the highest number

of people with different kind of health issues as a result of Boko Haram insurgency, kidnapping and related social unrest. As a result of this, any state in the north-east represents an important Nigeria's zone needful to operationalized public health institution in an efficient and effective manner.

Sample

A sample is a set of individuals or respondents selected from a larger population for the purpose of a survey (Salant & Dillman, 1994). To select sample for this study, cluster sampling technique will be employed. Cluster sampling is a sampling technique in which the entire population of interest is divided into groups or clusters and a random sample of these clusters is selected (Sarndal, Swenson & Wreman, 1992). The selected sample will represent the Population and is going to be economical as well. It is economical because the size of the sampled clusters is manageable in terms of cost and time. Time and cost are important considerations to researchers (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010).

Methods of Data Collection

This study will employ field study design where the research constructs will be examined. Cross-sectional survey method will be employed. Cross-sectional survey method is chosen for this study to avoid long time consumption that characterized the longitudinal research (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010). The researcher with assistance of employed assistants will distribute questionnaires to sample elements of selected public health institutions. Follow-ups using personal contact, telephone and email will be done to ensure timely completion for collection of distributed questionnaires. And as an inducement or motivation for quick response, each respondent will be given a biro with Bayero University Kano, Department of Business Administration and Entrepreneurship logo.

Measurement

To measure the existence of OCB this study will adapt the organization citizenship behaviour scale (OCBS) having sixteen items developed by (Lee & Allen, 2002). This scale is one of the most extensively used mechanisms that is used to measure OCB and is constructed to find OCB towards individuals (OCBI) and OCB toward organization (OCBO). This scale used in most prominent studies (Jain & Rizvi, 2018; Jin, McDonald, & Park, 2018; Lavy & Littman-Ovadia, 2017; Ong, Mayer, Tost, & Wellman, 2018; Piccolo & Colquitt, 2006; Saks, 2006). To ensure the clarity and make it more understandable to the respondents several modification may be consider rewriting the items.

Job satisfaction

Developing feelings of Job satisfaction for a variety of objects, material and immaterial in nature, thus job satisfaction will be measured using the shortened version of JDI (Smith et al., 1969). Five factors of job satisfaction were to be considering for the study (co-workers, supervisor, work, salary and promotion).

Servant Leadership

The servant leadership behaviours will be measured using the Liden RC, Wayne SJ, Zhao H, and Henderson D. (2008) seven dimension-models. The seven dimensions include helping subordinates grow and succeed, putting subordinates first, behaving ethically, and creating value for the community, emotional healing, empowerment, and conceptual skills. The Liden et al.'s (2008) measurement scale is going to be adopted in this study largely because the measure was reported to be the most valid instrument for measuring servant leadership considering the rigorous tests for validity and reliability it has gone through at development stage (Liden et al., 2008).

The Transformational and Transactional Leadership Style

Leadership instrument would be adapted from the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) form developed by Bass and Avolio (Bass BM, Avolio BJ 2000). The transformational leadership instrument will measures charisma, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and charisma exhibited by supervisors. While, the transactional instrument will measure management intervention and reward.

Measurement Scale

The Likert-type scale is considered more appropriate and reliable for measuring the respondents' perception and attitudes (Alreck & Settle, 1995; Miller, 1991). The instrument will be used to measure the key variables of the research study using a 7-point itemized scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). It was stated that 7-point measurement scale is more reliable (Krosnick & Fabrigar, 1997). They further stated that the scale also gives the respondents independence of expressing their feelings without limiting their choices.

CONCLUSION

Studies have suggested that servant leadership, transactional and transformational leadership behaviour influences employee Organizational citizenship behaviours (OCB), as job behaviours which are voluntary, not formally or directly

recognized by the organizational reward system, promote the effectiveness of the organization. The study also confirms that employees with high satisfaction were likely to portray positive behaviours such as OCB, since JS and OCB have been empirically found to promote the efficient and effective functioning of organizations. Therefore, job satisfaction could be a good mediator to the above mentioned construct, this is because, numerous studies have identified that job variables mediates the relationship between human resource management variables such as motivation and other job outcomes such as OCB.

This paper is an attempt to contribute to theory building of OCB and job satisfaction, leadership styles, as well as making meaningful contribution to human resource management practice. The paper therefore seeks to empirically assess the influence of servant leadership, transactional, transformational leadership style, and the job satisfaction on employees' willingness to engage in OCB by using the health institution in Bauchi State the north-east part of Nigeria. This paper will, therefore, bridge the literature gap by providing first-hand information regarding the relationship among the variables and OCB within a new research environment of the health sector and context (Nigeria). This study will provide a new cross-cultural perspective of the mediating role of job satisfaction, and leadership style-OCB.

The relationship will no doubt help to enrich the human resource organizational behaviour literature. However, this study would practically provide framework for improving socially and attractive efficient and effective functioning of the Nigeria's health sector, particularly the Public health institutions in North East. The model of this study would guide stakeholders of the sector to understand yet an additional important human resource management approach for influencing employee performance that has potential to assist the organizational management to achieve the current efficient and effective health sector reform in the country.

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